

Common Mental Disorders among Inmates of Old Age Homes in the Urban Field Practice Area of Raja Rajeshwari Medical College and Hospital, Bengaluru

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Abstract:

Background: Age is an important determinant of mental illness. The overall prevalence of mental and behavioural disorders tends to increase with age due to the normal aging of the brain, deteriorating physical health, and cerebral pathology. Disorders such as depression and cognitive disorders have a high prevalence in the elderly. Due to socio-demographic changes, older adults are forced to shift from their own place to some institutions/old age homes. The prevalence of these mental health disorders in old age homes is not well studied.

Methods: A descriptive study was conducted in seven old age homes of Urban Field Practice Area and 265 inmates participated in the study. The data was collected using a pretested, semi structured questionnaire. It was analysed using descriptive statistics.

Results: The majority of the inmates were of >80 years accounting for 38.49%. Females (63.39%) outnumbered the males (36.6%) and widows/widowers were 40.37%. 41.07% of female inmates were literate. Prevalence of diabetes mellitus and hypertension was 58.86% and 22.26% respectively. The prevalence of depression and dementia was 43.39% and 60.75% respectively.

Conclusion: The inmates of old age home have a high prevalence of depression and dementia. It is important to recognize these issues and manage them appropriately in the form of counselling, psychotherapy and essential medicines for better quality of life.

Keywords: Old age home, Depression, Dementia, Morbidity, Elderly.

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Introduction

Ageing is a normal, physiological, biological and universal phenomenon that happens in all the living beings. It is the process of maturing or becoming older. The population aged 60 years and above is considered to be old aged. It is a stage of life, distinct from the rest, characterized by physiological, psychological and social changes and leads to general reduction in functional capacities as well as structural changes in the body.

Globally, the number of people aged 65 or older is projected to grow from an estimated 524 million in 2010 to nearly 1.5 billion in 2050, with most of the increase in developing countries [1]. India has the second highest population of elderly people in the world. In India at present, older adults constitute 7.6% of total population and are projected to rise to

12% of the total population by 2021 [2]. The number of older adults was 43 million in 1981 and increased to 92 million in 2011 and is expected to triple in the next four decades i.e., 316 million [3]. The overall prevalence of mental and behavioural disorders tends to increase with age due to the normal ageing of the brain, deteriorating physical health and cerebral pathology [4].

Multiple factors are known to affect mental health in old age. Female sex, low education or illiteracy, being widow/widower/divorcee, medical comorbidities, loss of close relatives, social network, previous status in society, poor socio-economic status and disability are all well established as playing significant role in psychiatric illnesses among elderly [4,5,6,7]. Urbanization,

modernization, industrialization, and globalization have brought major transformations in the family in the form of structural and functional changes⁸. As a result of these socio-demographic changes, older adults at times are forced to shift from their own place to some institutions/old age homes [8,9]. Among these group of people, Psychiatric morbidity is frequently encountered and is severe and diverse.

The most common psychiatric morbidities in the Indian set up are Depression, Adjustment Disorders, Anxiety Disorders, Dementia and Delirium (Cognitive Disorders), Psychoses, Bipolar Disorders and Substance-related psychiatric illnesses [4,5]. Epidemiological data about these disorders in this population is still scarce, despite a few studies conducted in the recent past⁴. These illnesses cause increased morbidity in this group of people and lead to decline in quality of life (QOL) and also increase mortality [3] and thus adversely affecting the health care system of the nation.

Hence, the present study was undertaken to determine the proportion of common mental health disorders like depression and dementia and factors associated with them among inmates of old age homes.

Methodology

The present cross-sectional study was conducted among the elderly population aged 60 years and above in old age homes in old age homes of urban field practice area of Raja Rajeswari Medical College and Hospital, Bengaluru for a period of 18 months. Inmates staying in old age homes for more than 6 months and giving informed consent were included in study. Inmates having difficulty in speech and communication were excluded from study. Before conducting the study, Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC) of Raja Rajeswari Medical College and Hospital. In this study, seven old age homes in the urban field practice area of Raja Rajeswari Medical College and Hospital were included. A total of 270 inmates were living in these seven old age homes.

The sampling method involved the following steps: Firstly, all old age homes within the urban field practice area of Raja Rajeswari Medical College, Bengaluru, were enlisted. Subsequently, the elderly population aged 60 years and above residing in these old age homes was enumerated. The number of inmates from each old age home is as follows: Old age home no. 1 had 65 inmates, Old age home no. 2 had 35 inmates, Old age home no. 3 had 33 inmates, Old age home no. 4 had 27 inmates, Old age home no. 5 had 59 inmates, Old age home no. 6 had 31 inmates, and Old age home no. 7 had 20 inmates, totalling 270 inmates. However, based on the inclusion criteria, only 265 inmates were

selected for the study, with 5 being excluded. All the old age homes included in the study were operated by Non-Government Organizations (NGOs).

The method of data collection was carried through interview method in which a semi structured, and pre-tested questionnaire was used to interview. Contents of the questionnaire were explained to the inmates and to the in-charge person and they were ensured that confidentiality will be maintained. The questionnaire includes sociodemographic details of study participants and assessment of depression, and dementia. Depression was assessed through the Geriatric Depression Scale, which consists of 15 closed ended questions, of Yes/No type. Score 1 point was allotted for each answer (A score >5 points is suggestive of depression). Dementia was assessed using Mini Mental Status Examination. This consists of 11 closed ended questions. Responses were scored, maximum score was 5 and minimum being 1 and total score was 30. Those who scored ≥ 24 was considered to have Normal Cognition and those who scored of 19-23 to have Mild Cognitive Impairment, those who Scored of 10-18 to have Moderate Cognitive Impairment and those who Scored of ≤ 9 to have Severe Cognitive Impairment.

Descriptive statistics were used to present the data. Quantitative variables were expressed in frequency, percentage and proportions and continuous variables were expressed in mean, standard deviation. Inferential statistics like Z test and Chi-Square tests were applied and p value < 0.05 is considered significant.

Results

Table 1 shows sociodemographic profile among inmates. Majority of Inmates belonged to the age group >80 years among them 39% were females and 37% were males. Majority of old age home inmates 236 (89%) were Hindus, 23 (9%) were Christians, 2% belonged to other religion. Majority of the females 69 (41%) had studied up to higher primary, and 33 (34%) of the males were graduates. Maximum number of old age home inmates 107 (40%) were widow/widower (60% were widows, and 7.21% were widowers).

Table 2 shows Characteristics of study participants. Majority of the inmates 90 (33.9%) were staying for a duration of 24-36 months. Maximum number of old age home inmates 118 (44.52%) were not having children, 42 (15.84%) were having only one child. Majority of the inmates 156 (59%) had Diabetes Mellitus, 59 (22%) had Hypertension, 39 (15%) had Osteoarthritis, 6 (2%) had cataract, 4 (2%) had Bronchial Asthma and only one had malignancy 1 (0.37%). Table 3 shows depression among study participants based on Geriatric depression scale (GDS). About 115 (43.39%) out

of 265 of old age home inmates were having a score of ≥ 5 in Geriatric Depression scale, and 150 (56.60%) were having score of < 5 . Table 4 shows that according to Mini Mental Status Examination, it was observed majority of them- 83 (31.32%) inmates scored 10-18, belonged to Moderate Dementia, 45 (16.98%) inmates scored 19-23 belonged to Mild Dementia, 33 (12.45%) inmates scored ≤ 9 belonged to severe Dementia.

Table 5 shows Factors associated with depression among study participants. Depression was more among inmates with the increasing age, female

gender, those who stayed for 24-36 months in old age homes, those inmates who had diabetes mellitus and those who were widow/widower. The shorter duration of stay was significantly associated with depression.

Table 6 shows the association between sociodemographic variables like age, gender, education, comorbidities, marital status and Dementia, there is a significant association between Education and Dementia, where p value is 0.015 and Marital status and Dementia, where p value is < 0.001 .

Table 1: Sociodemographic profile among inmates

Sociodemographic profile	Frequency (n=265)	Percentage
Age		
60-69	73	28.0
70-79	90	34.0
>80	102	38.0
Gender		
Male	97	37.0
Female	168	63.0
Religion		
Hindu	236	89.0
Muslim	01	0.3
Christian	23	8.6
Others (Buddhism, Jainism)	05	1.8
Education		
Illiterate	18	6.79
Primary	38	14.3
Secondary	84	31.6
Intermediate	45	16.9
Graduate	63	23.7
Post-graduate	17	6.41
Marital status		
Married with spouse alive	55	21.0
Separated	47	18.0
Widow/Widower	107	40.0
Divorced	09	03.0
Unmarried	47	18.0

Table 2: Characteristics of study participants

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Duration of stay (months)		
6-12	86	32.4
24 - 36	90	33.9
48 - 60	37	13.9
>60	52	19.6
No. of children for inmates		
Nil	118	44.0
01	42	16.0
02	54	20.0
03	31	12.0
≥ 4	20	8.0
Comorbidities		
Diabetes mellitus	156	58.8
Hypertension	59	22.2
Osteoarthritis	39	14.7

Cataract	06	2.26
Bronchial asthma	04	1.5
Malignancy	01	0.37

Table 3: Depression among old age home inmates based on Geriatric depression scale (GDS)

GDS	Frequency	Percentage
Depressed (GDS \geq 5)	115	43.39
Not depressed (GDS <5)	150	56.61

Table 4: Dementia among old age home inmates based on Mini-mental status examination

Dementia	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	>24	104	39.24
Mild	19-23	45	16.98
Moderate	10-18	83	31.32
Severe	\leq 9	33	12.45

Table 5: Factors associated with depression among study participants

Factors		Depressed	Not depressed	P value (<0.05)
Age	60-69	31	42	0.287
	70-79	34	56	
	>80	50	52	
Gender	Male	36	61	0.117
	Female	79	89	
Duration of stay (months)	06 - 12	34	52	0.018*
	24 - 36	44	46	
	48- 60	11	26	
	>60	26	26	
Co-morbidities	Diabetes mellitus	72	84	0.094
	Hypertension	29	30	
	Osteoarthritis	10	29	
	Cataract	1	5	
	Bronchial asthma	2	2	
	Malignancy	1	0	
Marital status	Married	20	35	0.406
	Separated	21	26	
	Widow/er	48	59	
	Divorced	2	7	
	Unmarried	24	23	

*P value <0.05 is significant

Table 6: Factors associated with Dementia among study subjects

Factors		Mild	Moderate	Severe	P value
Age	60-69	10	20	7	0.565
	70-79	17	20	9	
	>80	18	43	17	
Gender	Male	17	22	10	0.417
	Female	28	61	23	
Education	Illiterate	2	7	1	0.015*
	Primary	6	13	8	
	Higher primary	22	30	4	
	Intermediate	4	15	14	
	Graduation	9	16	5	
	Post-graduation	2	2	1	
Comorbidities	Diabetes	28	51	24	0.341
	Hypertension	10	27	9	
	Osteoarthritis	3	4	0	
	Cataract	2	1	0	
	Bronchial asthma	1	0	0	
	Malignancy	1	0	0	
Marital status	Married	11	8	11	<0.001*

Separated	13	5	11
Widower	16	45	9
Divorced	1	5	0
Unmarried	4	20	2

*P value <0.05 is significant

Discussion

In this study, out of 265 old age home inmates, 38% were in the age group of >80 years followed by 34% in the age group of 70 – 79 years and 28% inmates were in the age group of 60 - 69 years. The mean age of the old age home inmates was 75.59 (± 8.05) years. A study done by Asadullah Md et al [11] showed similar findings: 42.2% were in the age group of 80 years and above. The mean age of male and female respondents were 75.3 (± 8.6) and 76.8 (± 7.7) respectively. In Rani AM et al [12] contrary results were seen, greater proportion of inmates (38.1%) were in the age group of 60–69 years followed by 70-79 years (36.2%) and then 80 years and above (25.7%).

Among the 265 inmates at the old age homes, 168(63%) were females and 97 (37%) were males. Similar results were seen in a study done by Bansod D et al. which was done at the old age homes of Maharashtra, which showed female predominance; 55% were females and 45% were males [13].

In this study it was found that 69 (41.07%) of females had studied up to secondary school, and 33 (34.02%) of the males were graduates. These findings were similar to a study done by Bindu M et al, where majority of females (40%) had studied up to secondary school and 50 % of males were graduates [14].

In this study it was observed that 35 (36.08%) of the males were staying in the old age home for a duration of 6 -12 months, and 57 (33.92%) of females were staying for a duration of 24-36 months. In a study done by Bindu M et al [14] majority of the male old age home residents (48%) were staying at the old age home for 1-5 years and only 17% of females were staying in old age home since <1year.

In this study it was observed that majority of old age home inmates- 236 (89.05%) were belonging to Hindu religion, 23 (9%) were belonging to Christian, and only 2% had belonged to other religion. In a study conducted by Satapathy et al [15] similar results were seen, majority of them (80%) belonged to Hindu religion, 18% of them belongs to Christian, and 2% of them belongs to Muslim religion. In Rao SS et al [16] majority of them 80% belonged to Hindu religion, 2% of them belonged to Christian and only 2% of them belonged to Muslim religion. In this study it was observed that majority of old age home inmates-

107 (40.37%) were widow/widower and 55 (20.75%) were married with spouse alive, 47 (17.73%) were unmarried and 47 (17.73%) were separated and 9 (3.39%) were divorced. Similar results were seen in a study by Asadullah Md et al [11] seen, 47 (70.1%) of females were either unmarried, widow or divorced and only 10 (43.4%) of males were either unmarried, widower or divorced.

In this study it was observed that 118 (44.52%) of old age home inmates were not having children, 42 (15.84%) were having only one child, 54 (20.37%) were having two children, 31 (11.69%) were having three children, 20 were having more than four children. This was similar to a study done by Bansod D et al [13] where 30% of the respondents did not have children.

In this study it was observed that 156 (58.86%) of the inmates had diabetes mellitus, 59 (22.26%) had hypertension, 39 (14.71%) had osteoarthritis, 6 (2.26%) had cataract, 4 (1.5%) had bronchial asthma and only one had malignancy (0.37%). This was different to a study done by Asadullah Md et al [11], where the common health problem was Hypertension (44.4%), followed by type 2 diabetes mellitus (36.7%).

In this study it was observed that 115 old age home inmates (43.39%) out of 265 had a score >5 in Geriatric Depression scale, and 150 (56.60%) had a score <5. The prevalence of depression in our study was found to be 43.39% which is similar to a study done by Kumar S et al [17], which showed a overall prevalence of depression to be 47.8% by using the Geriatric depression scale (GDS). In a study by Achappa et al [18], the magnitude of depression was found to be 50.5%.

In this study, the occurrence of depression increases with increasing age. The prevalence of depression in our study was found to be more in inmates who were relatively new to old age homes, who had lost their life partner and inmates without children. The duration of stay in old age homes was significantly associated with depression.

In this study it was observed that out of 265, 161 (60.75%) had dementia based on Mini mental status examination. Out of these, 45 (16.98%) inmates had a score of 19-23 suggestive of mild dementia, 83 (31.32%) of inmates had a score 10-18 in MMSE suggestive of moderate dementia, and 33 (12.45%) inmates scored ≤ 9 suggestive of severe dementia. In an Indian study by Nagaraj

AKM.et.al, it was found that cognitive impairment was seen in 46% of inmates in old age homes which was more than that in the community (36%) [4].

Out of 161 inmates in the study who had dementia, 37 were in the age group of 60-69 years, and 78 inmates were in the age group of >80 years. The occurrence of dementia increases with increasing age.

Conclusion

The prevalence of depression and dementia in this study was 43.39% and 60.75% respectively. The shorter duration of stay in old age home was significantly associated with depression. Dementia was significantly associated with higher primary education and inmates who lost their life partner.

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